

School of Archaeology, University of Oxford
24th September 2021
13:30–17:00h (GMT)

Resilience in Archaeological Research Different Concepts & their Potentials

Hybrid Workshop

Caroline Heitz, Astrid Nyland, Martin Renger & Amy Bogaard

Registration: caroline.heizt@arch.ox.ac.uk

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Resilience in Archaeological Research – Different Concepts and their Potentials

Workshop*

By Caroline Heitz, Astrid Nyland, Martin Renger & Amy Bogaard

In recent years, resilience has become a key term in social science debates on how to cope with major societal challenges ranging from the COVID-19 pandemic to climate change. Originating as a concept in psychology, ecology and engineering, resilience research has become a broad inter- and transdisciplinary field reaching from risk management to ancient studies. The diversity of disciplines is reflected in an equally great variety of concepts and methodologies, from taking resilience as an interpretative metaphor to system-theoretical approaches that are used for agent-based predictive modelling.

In this workshop the conceptual and methodological potential of this variety for archaeological empirical research will be discussed based on four papers. The first two papers are examples of different resilience concepts that have already been used in archaeology; the last two papers contain resilience concepts from other disciplines which could open up new fields of inquiry in archaeological research and accordingly, their transferability and operationalization in case studies will be discussed. Furthermore, related concepts such as vulnerability, sustainability or fragility will also be addressed. While this workshop aims at giving an introduction to resilience research, it also offers the chance to explore new avenues for those of you working on similar topics.

The papers might be read by the participants in preparation but will also be introduced by short impulse talks of about 15 minutes each followed by 20 minutes of moderated discussion.

The workshop is open to the School of Archaeology staff and research students as well as interested parties from other universities. For registration and questions please contact: caroline.heitz@arch.ox.ac.uk

* The workshop will be hybrid or held online, details, including venue specification, will be announced later.

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Programme

13:30h **Introduction**

Paper 1: Resilience theory & the adaptive cycle

13:40h Amy Bogaard

Bogaard, A. et al. 2017, Agricultural innovation and resilience in a long-lived early farming community: the 1,500-year sequence at Neolithic to early Chalcolithic Çatalhöyük, central Anatolia. Anatolian Studies, Vol. 67, 2017, pp. 1 - 28.

Paper 2: Spatial mobility & community resilience

14:20h Caroline Heitz

Heitz, C. et al. 2021, Mobility as resilience capacity in northern Alpine Neolithic settlement communities. Archaeological Review from Cambridge, Vol. 36.1: Resilience & Archaeology, 2021, p. 75 - 105.

15:00h ca. 20 min. break

Paper 3: Translocality & social resilience

Astrid Nyland

Sterly, H. et al. 2016, Migration for human security? The contribution of translocality to social resilience. Georgetown Journal of Asian Affairs, Vol. 3.1, 2016, p. 57 - 66.

Paper 4: Socio-spatial dimensions of resilience

Martin Renger

Christmann, G. b., Ibert, O., 2012, Vulnerability and resilience in a socio-spatial perspective. A social-scientific approach. Raumforschung und Raumordnung 70, 2012, p. 259 -72.

16:40h **Final discussion**

Organization & Affiliations

This workshop is organized in the scope of Caroline Heitz' SNSF-Postdoc.Mobility Fellowship "*Time and Temporality in Archaeology. Approaching Rhythms and Reasons for Societal (Trans)formations in Prehistoric Central Europe (TimeArch)*" funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) (<http://p3.snf.ch/project-194326>). Her project focuses on social archaeology, mobility and translocality as well as vulnerability and resilience of Neolithic settlement communities in relation to climatic change. In this framework she is working in Prof. Amy Bogaard's team as a Research Associate at the School of Archaeology, University of Oxford. Astrid Nyland and Martin Renger, archaeologist who are contributors to the shared TRAVAS blog and workshop (<http://resilience2020.archaeological.science/>) are invited as discussants.

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